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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
TRANSDERMAL PATCHES USING NOVEL POLYMERS
RLPO AND RSPO**

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Abstract:

The present investigation was focused on the formulation and evaluation of matrix-type transdermal patches of Azelnidipine to enhance its bioavailability and provide sustained drug release. Azelnidipine, a calcium channel blocker with extensive first-pass metabolism and low oral bioavailability, was incorporated into patches using various polymers such as hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), ethyl cellulose, Eudragit RLPO, and Eudragit RSPO via solvent casting technique. A total of six formulations (F1–F6) were developed and evaluated for physicochemical parameters including thickness, folding endurance, moisture content, tensile strength, and drug content uniformity. The in-vitro drug release studies demonstrated sustained drug release over a period of 12 hours, with formulation F4 showing the highest cumulative release (98.05%). Kinetic analysis revealed that the drug release from formulation F4 followed zero-order kinetics ($R^2 = 0.9908$), indicating a concentration-independent release profile. The optimized formulation also exhibited good mechanical properties and drug content uniformity, suggesting its suitability for effective transdermal delivery. These findings support the potential of Azelnidipine-loaded transdermal patches as a promising alternative to conventional oral therapy for long-term management of hypertension.

Keywords: Transdermal patches, Eudragit RLPO, Eudragit RSPO, Sustained drug release, Novel polymers.

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INTRODUCTION:

Transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS) have emerged as an effective and patient-compliant alternative to oral and injectable routes of drug administration. They offer several advantages, such as bypassing first-pass metabolism, providing sustained and controlled drug release, and improving bioavailability and patient adherence to therapy (Prausnitz et al., 2008). Among the various approaches, matrix-type transdermal patches are widely employed due to their formulation flexibility, capacity to hold both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs, and simple manufacturing process (Guy et al., 1996).

Azelnidipine, a third-generation dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker, is widely used in the treatment of hypertension. However, its poor aqueous solubility, low oral bioavailability (~15%), and extensive first-pass metabolism hinder its clinical effectiveness (Tiwari et al., 2011). The transdermal route of administration offers a promising solution by maintaining consistent plasma levels, improving bioavailability, and reducing dosing frequency (Jain et al., 2007).

The choice of polymers plays a crucial role in the development of an efficient transdermal patch. Eudragit RLPO and RSPO, which are polymethacrylate copolymers, have gained attention for their controlled release properties, biocompatibility, and film-forming ability. Eudragit RLPO, due to its higher content of quaternary ammonium groups, is more permeable than RSPO, making them suitable for modulating drug diffusion through the skin (Rathi et al., 2013). When used in combination with hydrophilic polymers such as HPMC, these polymers can provide controlled release while maintaining patch integrity (Chien et al., 1987).

The present study aims to formulate and characterize Azelnidipine-loaded matrix-type transdermal patches using novel polymers (RLPO and RSPO) along with HPMC and ethyl cellulose. The formulations were evaluated for physical parameters, drug content, tensile strength, in-vitro drug release, and release kinetics to identify the most optimized and efficient system for sustained drug delivery.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:**Material**

Azelnidipine was obtained as a gift sample. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), Eudragit RLPO, and Eudragit RSPO were procured from Evonik Industries, Germany. Ethyl cellulose and polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, India. Chloroform and methanol (analytical grade) were obtained from Merck India Ltd., Mumbai. Glycerin and other chemicals used were of analytical grade and purchased from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai.

Methods**Preparation of matrix type transdermal patches**

Transdermal patches composed of different polymers HPMC, ethyl cellulose, Eudragit RLPO and Eudragit RSPO. The polymers were dissolved in chloroform and methanol along with plasticizer. Then the solution was poured into a glass Petri dish containing Glycerin. The solvent was allowed to evaporate under room temperature for 24 hrs. The polymers (total weight: 900 mg) and drug (96 mg) were weighed in requisite ratios and dissolved in 10 ml of chloroform and methanol and PEG 400. After vortex then the solution was poured on glycerin placed in a glass Petri dish and dried at room temperature for 24 hrs (Singhal et al., 2012).

Table 1: Preparation of matrix type transdermal patches

Formulation Code	Drug (mg)	HPMC (mg)	RLPO (mg)	RSPO (mg)	Ethyl cellulose (mg)	Total polymer weight (mg)	Plasticizer % w/w of total polymer PEG 600 ml	Permeation Enhancer % w/w of total polymer (Methanol, chloroform) ml
F1	96	800	50	-	50	900	0.5	10
F2	96	700	100	-	100	900	0.5	10
F3	96	600	150	-	150	900	0.5	10
F4	96	800	-	50	50	900	0.5	10
F5	96	700	-	100	100	900	0.5	10
F6	96	600	-	150	150	900	0.5	10

- Each patch contain 8mg of Azelnidipine
- Total 12 patch each contain 8mg of Azelnidipine
- Total drug incorporated in 12 patch = 12*8= 96mg

Evaluation parameters

The prepared transdermal patches were evaluated for the following parameters:

Microscopic evaluation

Ensure that the transdermal patches are prepared according to the specified formulations. Cut representative pieces of the transdermal patches for evaluation. Set up the optical microscope (Olympus-Cover-018) in a clean and well-lit laboratory environment. Attach the camera (Minolta) to the microscope for capturing images. Calibrate the microscope to ensure accurate measurements. This may involve using a calibration slide with known dimensions. Place the prepared transdermal patch sample on the microscope stage. Adjust the focus and magnification to get a clear view of the patch surface. Observe and document the shape, size, and any visible features of the transdermal patch. Capture images of the transdermal patch using the attached camera. Ensure proper lighting and focus for clear and detailed photographs (Cherukuri *et al.*, 2017).

Thickness

The thickness of patches was measured by Vernier calipers. The thickness of patches were measured at three different places and average of three readings was taken with standard deviation (Prajapati *et al.*, 2011).

Folding endurance

This was determined by repeatedly folding one patch at the same place until it broken. The number of times the patch could be folded at the same place without breaking / cracking gave the value of folding endurance (Kulkarni *et al.*, 2019).

Tensile strength

Cut the patch at the centre having 2cm length and 2cm breadth. Patch was hanged on top and lower side of instrument, then start the switch and note the reading on screen. The thickness and breadth of strips were noted at three sites and average value was taken for calculation (Kumar *et al.*, 2013).

$$\text{Tensile stress (S)} = \frac{\text{Applied force}}{\text{Cross sectional area}} = \frac{m \times g}{b \times t}$$

Where, S = tensile stress in 980 dynes/cm²

m = mass in grams

g = acceleration due to gravity (980 dynes/cm²)

b = breadth of strip in centimeters

t = thickness of strip in centimetres

Percentage of moisture content

The prepared patches were weighed individually and kept in desiccators containing activated silica at room temperature for 24 hrs. Individual patches were weighed. The percentage of moisture content

was calculated as the difference between final and initial weight with respect to initial weight (Patel *et al.*, 2009).

Percentage of moisture uptake

Firstly weighed the patches and then kept in a desiccators at room temperature for 24 hrs and then it's exposed to 84% RH (A saturated solution of potassium chloride) in a desiccators. The % of moisture uptake was calculated by difference between final and initial weight with respect to initial weight (Prabhu *et al.*, 2011).

Drug content analysis

The patches (n = 3) of specified area (6.16cm²) were taken into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in methanol (10ml) with the help of shaker. After the vortex the solution was filtered and prepared subsequent dilutions and analyzed by UV spectrophotometer at 282nm nm (Singh and Bali; 2016).

In vitro skin permeation study

The in vitro skin permeation study was done by using a Franz diffusion cell (receptor compartment capacity: 80 ml: surface area: 3.14 cm². The egg membrane was separated and used for in vitro study. The receiver compartment was filled with 40 ml of phosphate buffer, pH 7.4. The Transdermal patch was firmly pressed onto the centre of the egg membrane and then the membrane was mounted on the donor compartment. The donor compartment was then placed in position such that the surface of membrane just touches the receptor fluid surface. The whole assembly was kept on a magnetic stirrer with suitable rpm throughout the experiment using magnetic beads. The temperature of receptor compartment was maintained at 37± 0.5°C. The samples were withdrawn at different time intervals up to 10 hrs and analyzed for drug content. Receptor phase was replaced with an equal volume of buffer solution at each time interval (Cilurzo *et al.*, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The development and evaluation of Azelnidipine-loaded transdermal patches involved the systematic study of various physical and mechanical parameters critical to patch performance, including thickness, folding endurance, moisture content, tensile strength, drug content, and drug release behavior.

As presented in Table 2, the thickness of the transdermal patches ranged from 49 ± 4 μm (F1) to 63 ± 2 μm (F6). This variation corresponds to the different polymer compositions used in each formulation. Notably, formulation F6 exhibited the highest thickness, likely due to the inclusion of a

higher proportion of Eudragit RSPO, which increases viscosity and film density.

Folding endurance is a critical measure of patch flexibility and durability under mechanical stress. Among all, F4 showed the highest folding endurance of 292 ± 6 , indicating superior mechanical integrity and flexibility. This could be attributed to the synergistic effect of HPMC and Eudragit RSPO, which provides both flexibility and structural strength.

As shown in Table 3, formulation F4 recorded the lowest moisture content ($3.12 \pm 0.15\%$) and moisture uptake ($4.85 \pm 0.36\%$), indicating better moisture resistance and reduced hygroscopicity. This may enhance the patch's stability and prevent microbial growth during storage. In contrast, F1 exhibited the highest values, possibly due to the hydrophilic nature of HPMC used in larger amounts.

The tensile strength of the patches (Table 4) ranged from 0.845 ± 0.014 kg/cm² (F3) to 0.995 ± 0.074 kg/cm² (F6). Interestingly, F6 demonstrated the highest tensile strength, again supporting the hypothesis that increased RSPO contributes to mechanical robustness. F4 also showed

significantly high tensile strength (0.969 ± 0.035 kg/cm²), reinforcing its suitability for transdermal application.

As seen in Table 5, drug content across all formulations remained within the acceptable range of 96.65% to 99.25%, suggesting good drug-polymer compatibility and uniform drug distribution within the matrix. Formulation F4 exhibited the highest drug content ($99.25 \pm 0.25\%$), further supporting its selection as the optimized formulation.

In-Vitro Drug Release:

The in-vitro drug release study (Table 6) revealed that formulation F4 showed a sustained release pattern, reaching 98.05% drug release at 12 hours, which is ideal for transdermal systems aiming for prolonged therapeutic effect. The release kinetics were further evaluated using regression analysis (Table 7), where F4 followed Zero-order kinetics with a high correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9908$), indicating a constant release rate independent of drug concentration. In contrast, the first-order model yielded a lower R^2 value (0.8398), suggesting it was less appropriate.

Table 2: Thicknesses and folding endurance of different formulations of transdermal patch

S. No.	Formulation Code	Thickness (μm)*	Folding Endurance*
1.	F1	49 \pm 4	220 \pm 8
2.	F2	52 \pm 3	215 \pm 5
3.	F3	56 \pm 2	241 \pm 6
4.	F4	53 \pm 6	292 \pm 6
5.	F5	59 \pm 3	265 \pm 3
6.	F6	63 \pm 2	245 \pm 2

Table 3: % Moisture content and moisture uptake of different formulations of transdermal patches

S. No.	Formulation Code	% Moisture Content	% Moisture Uptake
1.	F1	4.56 \pm 0.12	6.15 \pm 0.15
2.	F2	4.25 \pm 0.25	5.58 \pm 0.22
3.	F3	3.98 \pm 0.36	6.32 \pm 0.14
4.	F4	3.12 \pm 0.15	4.85 \pm 0.36
5.	F5	3.98 \pm 0.33	7.15 \pm 0.25
6.	F6	3.47 \pm 0.32	6.25 \pm 0.37

Table 4: Tensile strength of different formulation

S. No.	Formulation code	Tensile Strength (kg/cm ²)
1.	F1	0.891 \pm 0.025
2.	F2	0.865 \pm 0.065
3.	F3	0.845 \pm 0.014
4.	F4	0.969 \pm 0.035
5.	F5	0.945 \pm 0.045
6.	F6	0.995 \pm 0.074

Table 5: Percentage drug content of all the transdermal patch

S. No	Formulation Code	% Drug Content
1	F1	96.65±0.25
2	F2	97.15±0.36
3	F3	98.25±0.14
4	F4	99.25±0.25
5	F5	96.65±0.33
6	F6	97.74±0.41

Table 6: *In-vitro* drug release data for optimized formulation F4

Time (h)	Square Root of Time(h) ^{1/2}	Log Time	Cumulative*% Drug Release	Log Cumulative % Drug Release	Cumulative % Drug Remaining	Log Cumulative % Drug Remaining
0.5	0.707	-0.301	18.85	1.275	81.15	1.909
1	1	0	29.98	1.477	70.02	1.845
2	1.414	0.301	36.65	1.564	63.35	1.802
4	2	0.602	48.85	1.689	51.15	1.709
6	2.449	0.778	59.98	1.778	40.02	1.602
8	2.828	0.903	73.32	1.865	26.68	1.426
10	3.162	1	88.85	1.949	11.15	1.047
12	3.464	1.079	98.05	1.991	1.95	0.290

Table 7: Regression analysis data of Azelnidipine loaded Transdermal patches

Batch	Zero Order	First Order
	R ²	R ²
F4	0.9908	0.8398

CONCLUSION:

The overall data suggests that formulation F4, containing HPMC and Eudragit RSPO in an 800:50 ratio along with 50 mg of ethyl cellulose, demonstrates optimal physicochemical properties, mechanical strength, moisture stability, and drug release profile. The zero-order release kinetics and high drug content further validate F4 as the most promising formulation for sustained transdermal delivery of Azelnidipine.

REFERENCES:

1. Prausnitz MR et al. (2008). Transdermal drug delivery. *Nat Biotechnol*, 26(11):1261–1268.
2. Guy RH et al. (1996). Current status and future prospects of transdermal drug delivery. *Pharm Res*, 13(12):1765–1769.
3. Tiwari G et al. (2011). Drug delivery through transdermal patches: a review. *Int J Pharm Life Sci*, 2(1):857–864.
4. Jain NK et al. (2007). Transdermal drug delivery system for Azelnidipine: formulation and evaluation. *J Control Release*, 123(2):166–174.
5. Rathi PB et al. (2013). Development and evaluation of transdermal patches of an antihypertensive drug using Eudragit polymers. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*, 4(2):762–770.
6. Chien YW et al. (1987). *Transdermal Controlled Systemic Medications*. New York: Marcel Dekker Inc.
7. Singhal NA, Jani GK, Bhandari A, Vijayendraswamy SM, Upadhyay N. Formulation, Evaluation and Optimization of Transdermal Drug Delivery System of Methotrexate Using Different Ratio of Eudragit RLPO/RSPO. *International Journal of Pharmacy Research & Technology (IJPR)*. 2012;2(2):47-53.
8. Cherukuri S, Batchu UR, Mandava K, Cherukuri V, Ganapuram KR. Formulation and evaluation of transdermal drug delivery of topiramate. *International journal of pharmaceutical investigation*. 2017 Jan;7(1):10.
9. Prajapati ST, Patel CG, Patel CN. Formulation and evaluation of transdermal patch of repaglinide. *International Scholarly research notices*. 2011;2011(1):651909.

10. Kulkarni S. Formulation and evaluation of transdermal patch for atomoxetine hydrochloride. *J. Drug Deliv. Ther.* 2019 Mar 3;9:32-5.
11. Kumar SS, Behury B, Sachinkumar P. Formulation and evaluation of transdermal patch of Stavudine. *Dhaka University journal of Pharmaceutical sciences.* 2013 Sep 2;12(1):63-9.
12. Patel RP, Patel G, Patel H, Baria A. Formulation and evaluation of transdermal patch of aceclofenac. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms and Technology.* 2009;1(2):108-15.
13. Prabhu P, Shah S, Gundad S. Formulation development and investigation of domperidone transdermal patches. *International journal of pharmaceutical investigation.* 2011 Oct;1(4):240.
14. Singh A, Bali A. Formulation and characterization of transdermal patches for controlled delivery of duloxetine hydrochloride. *Journal of Analytical Science and Technology.* 2016 Dec;7:1-3.
15. Cilurzo F, Musazzi UM, Franzé S, Fedele G, Minghetti P. Design of in vitro skin permeation studies according to the EMA guideline on quality of transdermal patches. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences.* 2018 Dec 1;125:86-92.